

Research Article

Development of a Modular Low-Cost Wave Tank for Educational and Small-Scale Experimental Applications: A Practical Approach

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Abstract: This study presents the design and construction of a low-cost, modular wave flume developed as a physical model tool for hydraulics engineering and general physics education. The system aims to provide an accessible platform for observing basic wave phenomena and testing small-scale wave-structure interactions in a controlled environment. The wave flume consists of transparent acrylic panels, interlocking supports, a manually operated wave generator, with drainage system. Emphasis was placed on affordability, structural stability, ease of assembly, and scalability. A series of calculations were conducted to assess cost effectiveness. Results indicate that the system could be easily constructed at a low cost and can support future experimental studies involving wave mitigation structures. The proposed design offers a practical solution for institutions with limited laboratory resources, serving both instructional and experimental purposes.

Keywords: Engineering Education; Wave Tank; Teaching Aid.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Wave tanks are specially designed laboratory facilities utilized in examining surface gravity waves in a controlled setting. A proper setup consists of a long and narrow channel. A mechanical wavemaker is placed at one end and a wave absorber is installed at the other to ensure the reduction of wave reflection. Engineers utilize wave tanks to examine real-world issues in coastal and offshore areas. Such configurations allow physical modeling of wave energy systems, sediment transport, wave-structure interaction, and wave propagation. Wave tanks are also employed in education, allowing students and researchers to study the wave mechanics and hydrodynamic behaviour directly (Dean & Dalrymple, 1991). In other words, the wave tanks enable the researchers to study the wave behaviour, which is essential in water resources engineering, specifically coastal engineering. For instance, as Moon et al. (2022) highlighted, field-investigated data are crucial for understanding tsunami behavior. While field data are invaluable, laboratory-based physical modeling using wave tanks can provide controlled and repeatable simulations of tsunami wave mechanisms, supporting the development of effective mitigation and evacuation strategies. On the other hand, the modular wave tank may also serve as a cost-effective platform for evaluating material response under wave-induced loads in engineering studies, such as the properties and reaction of concrete, a primary material used in civil engineering. In conventional concrete studies, high-capacity hydraulic testing machines are used to assess compressive or tensile strength as conducted by Jing et al. (2024). In such case, the simplified flume systems can simulate wave-induced impact forces, providing complementary insights into structural behaviour in fluid–structure interaction scenarios, to further evaluate if the mixed concrete from new material is suitable for coastal structure such as seawall construction.

The specifications and size of wave tanks are often variable. Big wave tanks, occasionally over 30 meters in length, are built with reinforced concrete and equipped with advanced hydraulic or servo-controlled wave making systems. Though such facilities are available in institutions such as Universiti Kuala Lumpur (UniKL), and NAHRIM, and are very accurate and have the capability to be fitted with complicated testing, they are expensive, occupy big space, and cannot be easily modified to general academic use. For example, the RM12.7 million UniKL Hydrodynamic Wave Tank Centre, recognized globally as a facility under the 11th Malaysia Plan (RMK-11), is employed for offshore structure and ship model investigations. The tank measures 30 meters in length, 10 meters in width, and 6 meters in depth, and an additional 4 meters towards the center, and contains 20 paddles that have been designed to produce waves up to 0.5 meters in height, simulating 25–50-meter real waves (Malek, 2025). While the NAHRIM's MHI wave flume, 100 m long, 1.5 m wide, and 2 m deep. The flume is particularly designed to study wave effects on coast and offshore structures and sediment transport, and its wave generation system facilitates pertinent research (NAHRIM, 2023). In comparison, low-fidelity wave tanks, 2 to 4 meters in length, utilize less advanced components and are typically manually operated or controlled using low-end microcontrollers. Less precise but cheaper in price (RM 5,000 to RM 20,000), compact, and suitable for basic experiments and student projects.

There is a growing and unmet demand in Malaysia for a low-cost, removable, and portable wave tank that is suitable for use in schools and research laboratories with limited budgets. Current large-scale systems are not appropriate for use in secondary schools, technical colleges, or small university laboratories due to their cost and size. There is thus a strong need for a modular wave tank system that is transportable, assemble, and disassemble with ease. Precisely such a system—constructed from low-cost materials and powered by simple electric motors or open-source control systems—would provide sufficient functionality for hands-on education, basic hydrodynamic investigations, and preliminary model testing. This research aims to address that need by exploring the development of a modular low-cost wave tank that is practical, scalable, and suited to Malaysia's educational and engineering contexts.

The project objectives are as follow:

1. To design a portable wave tank using low-cost and readily available materials, suitable for use in educational and small-scale experimental settings.
2. To study the potential of the low-cost wave tank as a practical tool for teaching fundamental wave mechanics, coastal engineering concepts, and for small-scale model testing.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The water tank model is constructed using 10 mm thick acrylic boards, selected for their ability to withstand water pressure. The tank consists of 14 acrylic boards, including 8 sideboards, 1 front board, 1 end board, and 4 base boards as channel bed. 6 side connection boards and 3 base connection boards are used to reinforce the joints, enhancing the structural integrity. The assembly begins with bonding the 14 acrylic boards using chloroform-based acrylic glue. After curing, the boards are drilled and fastened with stainless steel screws, incorporating connection boards to ensure stability. To prevent water leakage, clear aquarium silicone sealant is applied along all joint interfaces. Additionally, anti-leak tape is used at high-risk joints to provide temporary sealing during experiments. Double-sided tape may be employed to hold components in place during initial assembly.

Figure 1. The wave tank model produced from AutoCAD with connecting boards.

A DC motor, connected to a DC power supply, is mounted at the front of the tank and coupled with an acrylic sheet serving as a wave generator. When activated, the motor drives the acrylic sheet to displace water, generating waves within the tank. To facilitate drilling and screwing, a side-by-side connection method is adopted, streamlining the assembly process. The combination of silicone sealant and anti-leak tape ensures a watertight seal, critical for reliable experimental outcomes. The DC motor will be hold in place with a structure formed by brick toy, available at a low price from e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Lazada. A hole in the end of the wave tank will be created to allow the discharge of water after use. This design optimizes structural strength, ease of assembly, and leak prevention, making the water tank model suitable for controlled wave generation studies.

3. FINDINGS

Table 1. Table of Quantity.

Item	Unit	Rate (RM)	Quantity	Total Price (RM)	Source
Acrylic Sideboard 500 mm x 300 mm x 10mm	Pcs	40.00-50.00	8	320.00-400.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Acrylic Front Board 320 mm x 300 mm x 10 mm	Pcs	30.00-40.00	1	30.00-40.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Acrylic End Board 320 mm x 300 mm x 10 mm	Pcs	30.00-40.00	1	30.00-40.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Acrylic Base Board 500 mm x 300 mm x 10 mm	Pcs	50.00-60.00	4	200.00-240.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Acrylic Side Connecting Board 100MM x 300M x 10MM	Pcs	10.00-20.00	6	60.00-120.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Acrylic Base Connecting Board 100 mm x 300mm x 10mm	Pcs	10.00-20.00	3	30.00-60.00	DY Double Y Enterprise (2025)
Anti Water Leak Tape 100 mm x 5000 mm	Pcs	5.00-10.00	2	10.00-20.00	Olynwen (n.d.)
DC Motor (12 V)	Set	20.00-25.00	1	20.00-25.00	Shopee Choice Global (n.d.)
Acrylics Glue (Chloroform) 60 ml	Bottle	5.00-10.00	2	10.00-20.00	Rainbow Art E Commerce (n.d.)
Clear Aquarium Sealant (Aquarium Silicon)	Bottle	10.00-15.00	2	20.00-30.00	Ember (n.d.)
Stainless Steel Screw and bolt (Size: M3, Length: 30 mm)	Set (10 bolts and nuts as a set)	5.00-10.00	6	30.00-60.00	relang01.my (n.d.)
Acrylic Sheet (Wave Generator) (A3, 2 mm width)	Pcs	10.00-15.00	1	10.00-15.00	WN Advertising MY (n.d.)
Double Sided Acrylic Foam Double Side Tape (3 mm width, 3 m long)	Roll	1.00-1.50	1	1.00-1.50	Unice Store (n.d.)
DIY Brick Toy (416 Pcs)	Set	20.00-25.00	1	20.00-25.00	Happy Toy Shop (n.d.)

PRICE RANGE: RM 791.00 TO RM 1096.50

The table of quantity in Table 1 shows the price breakdown of materials needed, with the total price not exceeding RM 1100 as compared to the wave flume priced from RM 5000 to RM 1 million. All the price listed above are obtained from direct quotation from online store seller and products available at e-commerce platform such as Shopee and Lazada and may varied from time to time, where the waivable shipping fee with free shipping vouchers is excluded in the table.

4. DISCUSSION

The wave tank is equipped with 10 mm thick acrylic panels to ensure structural integrity under hydrostatic and dynamic pressure and to minimize deformation that will impair test accuracy or cause long-term damage. Thinner panels would be less costly at the sacrifice of safety and accuracy, especially for wave or deep-water tests. Its most significant innovation is a modular, removable design made up of four identical sections that can be assembled as needed. That allows versatile arrangements: from small class use to the longer lab experiment, simple to carry, to keep and to share between different institutions. Such as, although a basic setting of two or three sections will suffice in small classes, a more advanced test which is designed to have five or six sections can utilize a university laboratory. This scalability also makes the tank highly portable, easy to store, and perfect for mobile demonstrations or shared use amongst institutions.

The wave tank has been designed for educational and small-scale research purposes in coastal and hydraulic engineering, which can be easily replicated by any institutions, not necessarily professional institutions or instrument suppliers. It allows for simple experiments such as wave propagation, reflection, transmission, wave–structure interaction, and the measurement of overtopping rates on all forms of coastal defence structures, from natural beach profiles to sea walls, revetments, rock armour, and submerged breakwaters. Though less precise than full-scale flumes, it is highly adapted for effective physical modelling for conception verification, parameter testing, and educational purposes. Ideal for use in student projects and STEM outreach, it leads to hands-on comprehension of the behaviour of waves and design accommodations in coastal defence.

The modular tank addresses a clear need in the Malaysian educational and research landscape, where cost and space limitations often restrict access to hydraulic lab equipment. With a targeted cost below RM 1,100, the tank offers a practical alternative to traditional flumes, which can cost over RM 1 million and require permanent installation space. This system is particularly suited for undergraduate engineering programs, secondary school science activities, and early-stage coastal research, where ease of use, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility are key priorities.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the modular and cost-effective design of a wave tank offers a realistic and cost-saving solution to stimulate coastal engineering study and research in Malaysia. Portable, low-cost, and adjustable, it is best suited to schools, technical schools, and universities, where students can experience the hands-on nature of wave behaviour and the principles of coastal protection which are typically absent from standard curricula. Its modularity offers simplicity of modification to accommodate most test requirements, with flexibility for both teaching and primary investigations.

For additional enhancement of the system performance, future development may include the addition of servo-controlled paddles or programmable wave generators to generate more accurate waves, in addition to Arduino or Raspberry Pi for automation and data logging. Additional features such as flow circulation systems and removable test models (e.g., piers, floating structures, seabed profiles) may also enhance the tank capabilities to undertake more advanced studies on wave–current interaction and structural response. With further development, it has the potential to become a standard

experimental apparatus in both teaching and applied research across civil, coastal, and marine engineering fields.

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